

Impact of k -, α -, and c -Eigenvalue Spectra on Group Constant Generation for Lead-Cooled Fast Reactor Transients

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ABSTRACT

The generation of few-group cross sections suitable for transient reactor simulations remains a key challenge in reactor physics. Traditional collapsing procedures rely on spectra obtained from k -eigenvalue calculations, while alternative formulations based on the α - and c -eigenvalues have recently been proposed as potentially more representative in time-dependent conditions. In this work, continuous-energy Monte Carlo simulations performed with SCONE are used to generate few-group constants employing the k -, α -, and c -spectra. The resulting data are then used in deterministic transient calculations with the FRENETIC multi-physics code, and compared against a Monte Carlo time-dependent reference. Results obtained for a Lead-cooled Fast Reactor (LFR) benchmark indicate that, for the analysed transient returning the system to criticality, the c -eigenvalue spectrum provides the most accurate reproduction of the reference kinetics, followed by the k - and α -based formulations. Furthermore, increasing the energy resolution from three to six groups reduces the discrepancy between the k - and c -based results, suggesting that their difference tends to vanish with finer group structures. These findings confirm the potential of alternative eigenvalue spectra for improving the physical consistency of few-group data in deterministic transient analyses.

Keywords: Eigenvalue spectra, Multi-Group Cross Sections, LFR, Monte Carlo, Nodal diffusion

1. INTRODUCTION

The generation of appropriate few-group constants for full-core, transient simulations — either based on diffusion or low-order transport approximations — remains a central challenge in reactor physics. Typically, the continuous-energy cross section for reaction x in energy group g is averaged preserving the associated reaction rate,

$$\Sigma_{x,g}(\vec{r}, t) = \frac{\int_{E_g}^{E_{g+1}} \Sigma_x(\vec{r}, E, t) \psi(\vec{r}, E, t) dE}{\int_{E_g}^{E_{g+1}} \psi(\vec{r}, E, t) dE}, \quad (1)$$

where ψ is a weighting function related to the neutron spectrum and the other symbols have their usual notation. Both in static and kinetic calculations, the weighting function is commonly taken as the steady state total flux computed for a set of representative core configurations. The resulting pre-computed libraries can be then interpolated. While this approach may be adequate for static evaluations, it introduces approximations in transient analyses, as the temporal variation of ψ is neglected to avoid the otherwise prohibitive cost of its direct computation.

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The time dependent, neutron balance equation without an external source is forced to steady state by introducing an eigenvalue that can be arbitrarily defined [1]. The most common choice is the well-known k -eigenvalue, where the effective multiplication factor k_{eff} is used to scale the fission source. However, less common alternatives exist, such as the α - and c - (also known as γ) eigenvalues. Each eigenvalue enforces steady state in a different way, depending on their definition, and thus they naturally produce different fundamental modes when the system simulated is not critical.

Given that multi-group constants (MGC) are generally collapsed using spectra from k -eigenvalue calculations, it remains an open question whether alternative eigenvalue spectra could yield significantly different group constants, and whether these differences meaningfully impact the results of deterministic simulations. Prior studies have started to explore this direction. As noted in [2] and [3], employing the time-eigenfunction $\varphi_\alpha(\vec{r}, E)$ may better capture the free temporal evolution of the neutron population, while maintaining computational costs comparable to standard k -based calculations.

A similar study was recently performed on a 3D Lead Fast Reactor (LFR) model, where 33-group MGC were generated with SERPENT 2 using a k -spectrum and subsequently collapsed to fewer group structures with the c and α spectra obtained via a deterministic multi-group diffusion solver written in FREEFEM++ [4]. These MGC were then employed to perform kinetic calculations with the FRENETIC code [5], showing that few-group data derived from non- k spectra can improve predictive accuracy.

Building on this foundation, the present work extends this investigation exploiting the continuous-energy Monte Carlo code SCONE [6] for a more rigorous generation of the MGC with the k -, α -, and c -eigenvalue spectra. The case study is the same 3D Lead Fast Reactor (LFR) core used in [4]. Transient simulations are then carried out with FRENETIC and compared against a SCONE time-dependent solution. Additionally, time-dependent MG cross sections are generated via Monte Carlo to provide an unbiased benchmark, enabling a comprehensive assessment of how different eigenvalue-based weighting functions influence the accuracy of few-group transient predictions.

2. THEORY

A compact formulation of the neutron transport equation is given by:

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{d\psi}{dt} + (L + C)\psi = (F + S)\psi, \quad (2)$$

where ψ is the angular neutron flux, t is time, v is velocity, and L , C , F and S are the streaming, collision, fission and scattering operators, respectively. In order to enforce steady state, one can define an eigenvalue and use it to scale the source term of the equation. For instance, the most common option is to use k to scale the fission source:

$$(L + T - S)\psi_k = \frac{1}{k} F\psi_k. \quad (3)$$

This equation returns the physical asymptotic neutron spectrum of the system when $k = 1$; otherwise, the energy spectrum of the resulting off-critical eigenmode will be biased compared to the energy spectrum of Equation (2) [7]. This is thoroughly explained in [7]: when the system is off-critical, the concentration of fission neutrons is artificially increased when $k < 1$ and decreased when $k > 1$. Since fission neutrons are localised in both energy and space, existing only at high energies and inside fissile materials, the $1/k$ scaling factor biases the resulting neutron flux distribution. Alternatively, one can reduce Eq. (2) to steady state by defining $\frac{d\psi}{dt} = \alpha\psi$, which is equivalent to assuming that the fundamental mode of the system decays in time as an exponential with decay constant α :

$$\psi_\alpha(r, \Omega, E, t) = \psi(r, \Omega, E)e^{-\alpha t}. \quad (4)$$

In this case, the steady state equation becomes:

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{v} + L + T - S \right) \psi_\alpha = F_\alpha \psi_\alpha. \quad (5)$$

In Eq. (5), an additional absorption term with cross section $\frac{\alpha}{v}$ was introduced; this term has a purely mathematical value, rather than being a physical event. [7] explains how this is equivalent to introducing a uniform scaling by α over the neutron population $n = \frac{\psi}{v}$, and as such it is unbiased: ψ_α is the physical asymptotic fundamental mode of the system, regardless of the initial state of the system. In this case, $\alpha = 0$ in a critical system, $\alpha > 0$ in a supercritical system and $\alpha < 0$ in a subcritical one. Details on the implementation of a Monte Carlo scheme to solve the α -eigenvalue equation can be found in [8, 9].

Another option is the c -eigenvalue, also occasionally called γ [10]. In this case, both the fission and scattering source are scaled by the eigenvalue:

$$(L + T)\psi_c = \frac{1}{c}(F + S)\psi_c. \quad (6)$$

Since, in most systems, the scattering source is considerably larger than the fission one, c will be systematically closer to 1 than k ; additionally, the scattering source is less localised than the fission source in both space and energy. These reasons suggest that the spectrum ψ_c should be less biased than ψ_k for off-critical systems. The c -eigenvalue equation can be implemented in a Monte Carlo code as explained in [11]. All eigenvalue formulations produce exactly equivalent eigenvectors when the reactor is critical.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Model description

The case study for this work is a simplified 3D model of an LFR, identical to the use used in [4]. The assemblies are homogenised both radially and axially into four materials: inner fuel (IF), outer fuel (OF), radial reflector (DA) and control rods (CR). The hexagonal lattice has a flat-to-flat pitch of 17.1 cm and the height of the core is 80 cm. Two configurations were defined for this work: a critical one, obtained by tweaking the inner fuel composition, and a subcritical one, both shown in Fig. 1. The subcritical configuration yielded a $k_{\text{eff}} = 0.94990 \pm 7$ pcm, corresponding to $c_{\text{eff}} = 0.99864 \pm 0.1$ pcm and $\alpha_{\text{eff}} = -1.41640 \cdot 10^4 \pm 4.79$ s⁻¹.

Figure 1. Sketch on the x - y plane of the core layout in the critical (left) and sub-critical (right) configurations. IF: inner fuel; OF: outer fuel; DA: dummy assembly (reflector); CR: control rod.

3.2. Cross section generation

The Monte Carlo code SCONE [6] was used for MGC generation. SCONE includes a k -eigenvalue solver, while a c -eigenvalue solver and the α - k iterative algorithm [8] were recently implemented. In

all cases, the group constants generation procedure follows the one described in [12], with the ‘flux-limited’ transport correction [13]. The group structures used are derived collapsing the ECCO33 group structure into 8, 6 and 3 groups, as shown in Table I. Different sets of group constants were generated for the two configurations shown in Fig. 1, with a material-wise resolution. All the eigenvalue calculations performed used 1 million particles per cycle; k used 30 inactive and 100 cycles; c used 1,000 inactive and 1,000 active cycles; α used 100 inactive and 100 active cycles. Fission source convergence was monitored by Shannon entropy in all cases.

Table I. Group boundaries in MeV adopted for the few-group calculations.

8G	19.640	$2.231 \cdot 10^0$	$4.979 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.111 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$2.479 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.531 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.035 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$7.485 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-11}$
6G	19.640	$2.231 \cdot 10^0$	$4.979 \cdot 10^{-1}$		$2.479 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.531 \cdot 10^{-3}$		$7.485 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-11}$
3G	19.640		$4.979 \cdot 10^{-1}$					$7.485 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-11}$

3.3. Reference transient calculation

In SCONE, critical source sampling [14] is used to generate the initial critical source of neutrons and precursors for kinetic MC calculations. A standard k -eigenvalue calculation is first performed to converge the fission source. During the final inactive cycle, neutrons and precursors are sampled and used to populate the initial kinetic source. Ideally, this whole process would be repeated to obtain an ensemble of kinetic sources and thus independent samples for statistical estimates. However, to reduce computational cost, SCONE instead samples kinetic sources from the same k -eigenvalue run (every m -th inactive cycle), accepting some correlation between samples in exchange for reduced runtime.

The k -eigenvalue calculation used 100,000 particles per cycle and 300 inactive cycles. The transient calculation used 100,000 particles per kinetic source and 5 kinetic sources, all sampled from the same k -eigenvalue run at intervals of 30 inactive cycles. The transient started from the critical configuration; at time 1.2 ms, a step control rod insertion was simulated, with a return to criticality at time 2.1 ms. A time step of 0.01 ms was used, for a total transient duration of 3.0 ms. Although this time step is larger than the typical prompt neutron lifetime ($\approx 10^{-7}$ s for LFRs) and thus insufficient to fully resolve prompt dynamics, it was selected as a compromise to limit computational cost. This study is therefore intended as a proof of concept, and future work will employ smaller time steps to better capture the prompt effects.

3.4. Deterministic transient calculations

The FRENETIC (Fast REactor Neutronics/Thermal-hydraulicS) code was used to perform the deterministic kinetic calculations. FRENETIC is a multiphysics code developed at Politecnico di Torino for the simulation of steady-state and transient behaviour of liquid metal-cooled fast reactor cores arranged in hexagonal closed assemblies. The code solves the multi-group diffusion model relying on a 3D coarse-mesh nodal expansion method, where each sub-assembly is represented by vertically stacked hexagonal prisms with one radial node per assembly. The neutronic module implements the fully implicit time discretisation scheme as well as advanced versions of the quasi-static method, equipped with an adaptive time-step selection [15]. To ensure consistency with the SCONE reference simulation, the implicit direct integration scheme was employed, using the same discretisation time step.

The kinetic simulations were performed using different sets of MGC, generated on the energy group structures listed in Table I and collapsed with the k -, c -, and α -spectra as weighting functions. In addition, a deterministic kinetic calculation was performed using the time-dependent MGC produced by SCONE, which scored a set of constants at each time step. The same critical initial condition is enforced rescaling the fission source by k , which is computed for any close-to-critical MG set analysed.

Given the inherent and systematic differences between multi-group diffusion and continuous-energy Monte Carlo transport, this deterministic calculation serves as an unbiased reference to assess which eigenvalue formulation, if any, best preserves reaction rates in time-dependent conditions.

4. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the ratio of the c - and α -spectra to the k -spectrum, which is taken as the reference. It can be observed that the ratio significantly deviates from unity across all materials and over most of the energy range—particularly in the thermal region—highlighting the importance of analyzing their impact on the MGC collapsing procedure.

Figure 2. Ratio of the c - and α -spectrum to the k -spectrum, assumed as a reference.

Figure 3 shows a comparison between the SCONE reference kinetic calculation and the ones computed by FRENETIC using the different MGC sets available. The MC and deterministic results are in general good agreement, considering the inherent approximations affecting the multi-group diffusion model. After the initial critical phase, the CRs are instantaneously inserted in the system, inducing a sharp power decrease. The two codes agree well, although FRENETIC presents a slower dynamics. After about 2 ms, SCONE predicts a faster power recovery than FRENETIC. This behaviour can be explained by the higher effective reactivity captured by continuous-energy transport, which more accurately represents the evolving neutron spectrum and angular flux during recriticality. In contrast, few-group diffusion models, based on pre-collapsed cross sections and isotropic approximations, tend to overestimate leakage and underpredict spectral hardening, leading to a slower response. Similar discrepancies between transport and diffusion dynamics have been reported in fast-spectrum transient benchmarks [16, 17].

Figure 3. Power evolution computed by SCONE and FRENETIC for the 3-group (top) and 6-group (bottom) MGC. Left: full transient. Right: zoom on the subcritical phase.

The FRENETIC scenarios show very similar overall trends. However, a closer inspection of the subcritical phase indicates that the c -eigenvalue formulation performs best in both the 3- and 6-group scenarios, as it most closely reproduces the reference FRENETIC simulation employing time-dependent MGC. The k -based formulation ranks second, while the α -based one provides the least accurate results. Overall, the MGC collapsed with the c -spectrum yields a faster and more realistic kinetic response, closer to the reference solution. It should be noted, however, that this ranking applies to the specific transient considered here, which returns the system to criticality. For transients driving the system toward a new asymptotic state, the α -spectrum would likely offer a more accurate representation, as it inherently accounts for the system's natural time-eigenmode behaviour. Moreover, when increasing the energy resolution from three to six groups, the k - and c -based results converge, suggesting that the difference between the two formulations tends to diminish as the energy discretisation becomes finer.

These observations are confirmed by the reactivity evolution in Figure 4, which are similar to what already observed in [4], although in a purely diffusion framework.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work investigated the impact of using alternative eigenvalue spectra —namely k -, α -, and c -based formulations— for the generation of few-group constants employed in deterministic kinetic simulations of a LFR. Continuous-energy Monte Carlo calculations performed with SCONE were used to produce consistent sets of multi-group constants, which were then adopted in the diffusion-based code FRENETIC and compared against a fully time-dependent Monte Carlo reference.

Results show that, despite the simplifications inherent to the multi-group diffusion model, the deterministic simulations reproduce the Monte Carlo transients with good overall agreement. Among the

Figure 4. Reactivity evolution computed by FRENETIC for the 3-group (left) and 6-group (right) for the sub-critical phase.

tested formulations, the c -eigenvalue weighting provided the most accurate reproduction of the reference power evolution, particularly during the subcritical phase, followed by the k - and α -based formulations. The use of c -collapsed constants yielded a faster and more realistic kinetics, closer to the reference solution. This behaviour, however, is specific to the transient considered here, which brings the system back to criticality. For transients leading towards a new asymptotic state, the α -spectrum would likely perform better, as it inherently captures the asymptotic time-eigenmode of the system.

Finally, increasing the energy resolution from three to six groups reduced the discrepancy between the k - and c -based results, suggesting that the difference between the eigenvalue formulations tends to vanish with finer energy discretizations. In spite of the limitations in this study, these findings confirm that alternative eigenvalue spectra can improve the physical representativeness of few-group data in transient analyses, while also highlighting the need for further studies on a broader range of reactor conditions and transient types.

Future efforts will be employed to study additional transient scenarios, investigating the adoption of different energy group structures as well as different reactor concepts. A special effort will be devoted to implement the different eigenvalue formulation in FRENETIC, in order to enforce criticality consistently with the eigenvalue used to produce the collapsed data.

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